

Enhancing Vehicle Damage Detection with MaskRCNN and Detectron2

Vishnu

Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
vishnuadrofficial@gmail.com

Nimmy Francis

Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
nimmyfrancis@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract: Automating vehicle damage detection is pivotal for the insurance, automotive, and maintenance sectors, where conventional manual checks are cumbersome and prone to inaccuracies. This paper presents a new automated car damage identification technique based on the powerful instance segmentation model Mask R-CNN. Our goal is to greatly improve damage assessments' accuracy and efficiency by utilizing the COCO vehicle damage dataset. The study verifies the precision of our method for identifying vehicle damage by delving deeply into the Mask R-CNN architecture and applying a carefully selected dataset enhanced by extra information. Our findings demonstrate how computer vision technology, particularly the Detectron2 framework, has the ability to revolutionize the way that vehicle damage assessments are performed. This study establishes the viability of automated damage identification, which is crucial.

Keywords—Mask R-CNN, Car Damage Detection, Detectron2, Instance Segmentation, COCO Car Damage Dataset, Data Augmentation, Gradio, Bounding Box Technique, Insurance Claims Management, Automated Vehicle Inspection, Deep Learning, Computer Vision, Fraud Detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adoption of automated vehicle damage detection systems is becoming more and more important in the changing automotive scene in order to expedite the procedures of assessment, repair, and insurance claim management. Although they are conventional, manual inspection techniques are very inefficient. Some of these inefficiencies include high processing times, biases, and human error. In order to overcome these obstacles, this article explores the combination of Mask R-CNN and Detectron2, a cutting-edge object detection framework created by Facebook AI Research, for the automatic identification of vehicle damage through digital photography. In order to show how deep learning and advanced instance segmentation can be used to improve damage detection accuracy, the study makes use of two large datasets: the Humans in the Loop Car Parts and Car Damages Dataset and the Coco Car Damage Detection Dataset.

Significantly, the introduction of image bounding box technology within this framework serves a dual purpose. First off, it improves damage detection accuracy, which makes damage assessment procedures more effective. Second, and perhaps most importantly for the insurance sector, it adds a strong fraud detection mechanism to the claims administration process. It is possible to precisely identify and match the car's number plate by using bounding box

algorithms to compare the uploaded damaged vehicle image with the real image of the vehicle stored in the insurance database. In addition to verifying the claim, this approach significantly reduces the possibility of false claims, protecting insurance firms from possible financial losses.

Moreover, the combination of Mask R-CNN's high fidelity in instance segmentation and Detectron2's integration for data preprocessing and evaluation highlights the significant advantages of utilizing cutting-edge technology to automate and improve damage assessment processes. In addition to improving the accuracy and efficiency of damage assessment in the automobile industry, this article seeks to demonstrate the revolutionary potential of integrating cutting-edge computer vision techniques to improve insurance claim handling procedures. This investigation has shown that the fusion of artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision technologies is crucial for negotiating the difficulties associated with manual damage assessments, signaling the beginning of a new era in auto diagnostics and insurance operations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The authors of the landmark paper [1] present Mask R-CNN, a framework that expands on Faster R-CNN's capabilities by adding a second branch for accurate object mask prediction in addition to the conventional bounding box detection. By precisely contouring objects with high-quality masks and identifying them inside an image, this discovery makes a significant contribution to the field of instance segmentation. Mask R-CNN shows amazing ease of use in training, low computational overhead, and adaptability in use, expanding its usefulness to applications other than object segmentation, like estimating a person's position. Without the need for intricate tactics, its performance surpasses all COCO tasks, establishing new standards for instance segmentation, object detection, and keypoint recognition.

On the subject of [2], was extremely important in benchmarking and promoting this field of study. includes pictures of damaged autos along with COCO (Common Objects in Context) comments for each image. These datasets are essential for training deep learning models, such as Mask R-CNN-based models that Detectron2 supports.

Detectron2 [3] from Facebook AI Research is a game-changing development in object detecting technology. This

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11525793](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11525793)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

next-generation platform, which is a total redesign of its predecessor, Detectron, is based on the fundamental maskrcnn-benchmark and includes a variety of cutting-edge detection algorithms. Detectron2 stands out due to its extensive collection of training recipes, which includes keypoint detection, panoptic segmentation, object detection, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation. Along with broad dataset support, it provides more than 80 pre-trained models for instant use or additional fine-tuning, including COCO, Cityscapes, LVIS, PASCAL VOC, and ADE20k. This extensive feature set and adaptability solidify Detectron2's standing as a key instrument in furthering object detection studies and applications.

Claims leakage poses significant financial challenges for insurance companies, largely due to inefficient processes and fraud. Leveraging advancements in AI, particularly deep learning, offers a promising solution. Dhieb et al. [4] propose a novel architecture combining deep learning and transfer learning to detect and localize vehicle damages efficiently. Their approach, utilizing the Inception-ResnetV2 model, demonstrates superior capability in identifying and classifying damage severity over traditional models, indicating a potential reduction in claims leakage through AI integration.

Accurately assessing vehicle damage after an accident is important in the world of auto insurance, but it frequently depends on manual assessment. In an effort to automate this evaluation procedure, Pasupa et al. [5] conducted a thorough investigation comparing five deep learning algorithms for the semantic segmentation of auto parts. According to their research, HTC with ResNet-50 is the best model for instance segmentation among various car types, obtaining a noteworthy mean average precision. They also evaluated how durable the algorithms were to changes in the environment, and GCNet proved to be the most resilient in these circumstances. The development of an automated method for evaluating automotive damage is made possible by these findings, which hold great promise for improving efficiency within the insurance industry.

With the aim of achieving major cost savings for insurance companies, Azmi et al. [6] present a ground-breaking Vehicle Damage identification System based on the YOLO v4 object identification framework. Their creative method was compiling a detailed dataset with a range of car defects, including dents and broken glass. Their model outperformed existing techniques with a remarkable mean Average Precision (mAP@50) of 81.20, obtained through intensive training and specialized preprocessing for YOLO v4. This study shows the system's effectiveness as well as its potential to completely change how the insurance industry evaluates damage.

III. MOTIVATION

The primary rationale for investigating advanced vehicle damage detection techniques with cutting-edge technologies like Mask R-CNN and Detectron2 is that there is an urgent need to tackle major issues in the automotive industry. This research is motivated by the possibility of greatly boosting vehicle safety standards, quickening accident response mechanisms, and increasing the effectiveness of insurance claim procedures. The application of computer vision technologies and the adaptability provided by open-source platforms like Detectron2 not only fit with the rapidly

changing artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision landscape but also hold the promise of major advancements in automated vehicle inspection systems. Such technological innovations are pivotal in enhancing the accuracy and reliability of damage assessment, thereby facilitating a more streamlined and fraud-resistant approach to insurance claims management. Alternatives are required for prompt intervention and early detection.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The pneumonia detection methodology makes use of pre-trained models for feature extraction and classification as well as deep learning algorithms, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The following is an outline of the process:

A. Data Collection:

An extensive dataset of automobile photos is put together, with each image annotated in COCO format. Images of cars with a variety of forms and severity of damage are included in this dataset. For the model to be trained to identify and correctly classify the variety of damage types found in real-world circumstances, the dataset's diversity is essential.

B. Data Preprocessing:

To ensure that it is ready for efficient training, the dataset is carefully pre-processed. It is divided into train, validation, and test sets. This division guarantees that the model is trained on a wide range of samples, which is essential for developing a strong model that can generalize effectively on untested data.

C. Model Selection:

The Mask R-CNN model is chosen because of its superior instance segmentation abilities, which are necessary for accurate car damage diagnosis and localization of the car damages. The training and assessment procedures are aided by the robust, open-source Detectron2 framework, which is built on PyTorch. Pre-trained weights from a large dataset formatted in COCO are used to enhance the model, improving its capacity to recognize and segment car damage from the onset.

D. Model training and evaluation:

In the training phase, the model minimizes the instance segmentation loss in order to learn how to discriminate between various car parts and forms of damage. A validation set is used to assess the trained model's efficacy using metrics like average precision (AP), which estimates the model's precision in recognizing and categorizing various forms of damage.

1. E. Inference and Damage Assessment:

The fully trained model is integrated with a user-friendly Gradio interface, which allows users to upload car images easily. The interface processes these images swiftly, displaying annotated results that highlight and categorize the detected damages, thereby facilitating immediate visual assessment.

F. Integration and User Interface:

The finalized model is deployed in real-world applications, where it is used for various purposes including managing insurance claims, maintaining vehicles, and aiding in accident response. The model's deployment also extends to mobile applications, allowing for on-the-go examinations and assessments of car damages.

2. G. Model Deployment:

The completed model is put to use in real-world settings, where it helps with accident investigation, insurance claim management, and vehicle maintenance, among other things. The model's rollout also includes mobile applications, enabling on-the-go vehicle damage inspections and evaluations.

V. BUILDING THE MODEL

A. Import:

CNN The Detectron2 framework, which integrates the Mask R-CNN architecture, is used to build the model for detecting car damage. The main procedures for building and applying this model are listed below:

```
from matplotlib.pyplot import axis

import requests
import numpy as np
from torch import nn
import requests
import torch
import detectron2
from detectron2 import model_zoo
from detectron2.engine import DefaultPredictor
from detectron2.config import get_cfg
from detectron2.utils.visualizer import Visualizer
from detectron2.data import MetadataCatalog
from detectron2.utils.visualizer import ColorMode
```

Detectron2: Facebook AI Research (FAIR) has developed an advanced open-source computer vision library. One of its features is the model_zoo module, which provides a range of pre-trained models suited for various computer vision applications.

2. COCO Dataset Tools: For managing datasets formatted in the COCO (Common Objects in Context) standard—which is widely used in tasks including object detection, segmentation, and captioning—the pycocotools library offers indispensable Python utilities.

B. Training:

The creation of an evaluator for performance evaluation and the setup of a data loader that includes data augmentations are made easier by the Trainer class in Detectron2. These augmentations are critical for enhancing the model's ability to generalize from the training data to real-world scenarios.

```
# create trainer with evaluation and augmentation
# https://github.com/facebookresearch/detectron2/blob/main/tools/train_net.py
class Trainer(DefaultTrainer): # inherit from default trainer
    @classmethod
    def build_evaluator(cls, cfg, dataset_name, output_folder=None):
        if output_folder is None:
            output_folder = os.path.join(cfg.OUTPUT_DIR, "evaluation")
        return COCOEvaluator(dataset_name, ["bbox", "segm"], output_folder)
    @classmethod
    def build_train_loader(cls, cfg):
        augs = [
            T.ResizeShortestEdge((cfg.INPUT_MIN_SIZE_TRAIN, cfg.INPUT_MAX_SIZE_TRAIN, cfg.INPUT_MIN_SIZE_TRAIN_SAMPLING),
                                T.RandomFlip(prob=0.5, horizontal=True, vertical=False),
                                T.RandomRotation([-90, 90]),
                                T.RandomLighting(0.5))
        ]
        mapper = DatasetMapper(cfg, is_train=True, augmentations=augs)
        return build_detection_train_loader(cfg, mapper=mapper)
```

```
# list of config: https://github.com/facebookresearch/detectron2/blob/main/detectron2/config/default.py
cfg = get_cfg()
cfg.merge_from_file(model_zoo.get_config_file("COCO-InstanceSegmentation/mask_rcnn_R_50_FPN_3x.yaml"))
cfg.DATASETS.TRAIN = ("dataset_train",)
cfg.DATASETS.TEST = ("dataset_val",)
cfg.DATASETS.NUM_CLASSES = 2 + 1 # 1 is empty
cfg.MODEL.WEIGHTS = model_zoo.get_checkpoint_url("COCO-InstanceSegmentation/mask_rcnn_R_50_FPN_3x.yaml") # (in training initialize from model zoo)
cfg.SOLVER.IMS_PER_BATCH = 2 # this is the real "batch size" commonly known to deep learning people
cfg.SOLVER.MAX_ITER = 20000 # 20000 iterations seems good enough for this toy dataset; you will need to train longer for a practical dataset
cfg.SOLVER.STEP_SIZE = 10000 # do not decay learning rates
cfg.MODEL.BACKBONE_FREEZE = True # the "frozen batch size" 128 is faster, and good enough for this toy dataset (default: 32)
cfg.MODEL.RESNETS.NUM_CLASSES = 2 # only use one class (empty) (see https://detectron2.readthedocs.io/en/latest/tutorials/train_net.html#update-the-config-for-new-datasets)
# NOTE: this config uses the number of classes, but a few popular unofficial tutorials incorrect uses num_classes here.
cfg.TEST.EVAL_PERIOD = 2000 # eval every 2000 iter
# Clear any logs from previous runs
import shutil
try:
    shutil.rmtree(cfg.OUTPUT_DIR)
except:
    print("no folder found, pass")
os.makedirs(cfg.OUTPUT_DIR, exist_ok=True)
trainer = Trainer(cfg)
trainer.resume_or_load(resume=False)
trainer.train()
```

C. Evaluation and Inference:

Applying the object detection model to each picture file path, loading the list, and superimposing the predictions on the images are the steps involved in the evaluation and inference process. By presenting thorough annotations that classify and highlight the distinct regions of damage on each car, this method enables a visual assessment of the observed problems.

A methodical approach to creating a strong model that can accurately detect and analyze vehicle damage is ensured by this methodology.

```
cfg.MODEL.WEIGHTS = os.path.join(cfg.OUTPUT_DIR, "model_final.pth") # path to the model we just trained
cfg.MODEL.ROI_HEADS.SCORE_THRESH_TEST = 0.7 # set a custom testing threshold
predictor = DefaultPredictor(cfg)
```

```
evaluator = COCOEvaluator("dataset_val", output_dir="./output")
val_loader = build_detection_test_loader(cfg, "dataset_val")
print(inference_on_dataset(predictor.model, val_loader, evaluator))
# another equivalent way to evaluate the model is to use "trainer.test"
```

```
def show_instances(img,
                  masks = predictor(img),
                  vis = Visualizer(img, {"": 1}),
                  metadata=MetadataCatalog.get(cfg.MODEL.METAFILE_DIR),
                  scale=0.5,
                  **kwargs):
    # remove the colors of unsegmented pixels, this option is only available for segmentation models
    img = x.draw_instances(predictor(img), metadata, **kwargs)
    plt.figure(figsize=(8, 8))
    plt.imshow(img)
    plt.axis('off')
    plt.show()
    masks = masks[0].cpu().numpy().astype('uint8')
    total_area = metadata.get('total_area')
    plt.text(10, 10, f'number of masks: {len(masks)} | total_area: {total_area}, fontsize = 40, color = "white", bbox = dict(facecolor = "red", alpha = 0.5)')
    plt.imshow(img)
    plt.show()
    plt.imshow(img)
    plt.show()
```

VII. RESULTS

```
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.fast_eval_api]: Evaluate annotation type "bbox"
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.fast_eval_api]: COCOeval_opt.evaluate() finished in 0.01 seconds.
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.fast_eval_api]: Accumulating evaluation results...
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.fast_eval_api]: COCOeval_opt.accumulate() finished in 0.00 seconds.
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all | maxDets=100 ] = 0.463
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50 | area= all | maxDets=100 ] = 0.155
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.75 | area= all | maxDets=100 ] = 0.438
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= small | maxDets=100 ] = 0.000
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area=medium | maxDets=100 ] = 0.025
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= large | maxDets=100 ] = 0.109
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all | maxDets= 1 ] = 0.050
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all | maxDets= 10 ] = 0.075
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all | maxDets=100 ] = 0.075
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= small | maxDets=100 ] = 0.000
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area=medium | maxDets=100 ] = 0.054
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= large | maxDets=100 ] = 0.110
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.coco_evaluation]: Evaluation results for bbox:
AP | AP50 | AP75 | A
Fig. 1. Result of Evaluating #notation type "boundary bo. Read more
```

Fig.1. Result of Evaluating annotation type “boundary box (bbox)”

```

[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.fast_eval_api]: Evaluate annotation type 'segm
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.fast_eval_api]: COCOeval_opt.evaluate() finished in 0.01 seconds.
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.fast_eval_api]: Accumulating evaluation results...
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.fast_eval_api]: COCOeval_opt.accumulate() finished in 0.00 seconds.
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all | maxDets=100 ] = 0.061
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50 | area= all | maxDets=100 ] = 0.129
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.75 | area= all | maxDets=100 ] = 0.054
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= small | maxDets=100 ] = 0.000
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area=medium | maxDets=100 ] = 0.040
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= large | maxDets=100 ] = 0.090
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all | maxDets= 1 ] = 0.071
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all | maxDets= 10 ] = 0.100
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all | maxDets=100 ] = 0.100
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= small | maxDets=100 ] = 0.000
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area=medium | maxDets=100 ] = 0.100
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= large | maxDets=100 ] = 0.110
[04/11 21:24:21 d2.evaluation.coco_evaluation]: Evaluation results for segm:
AP | AP50 | AP75 | AR
-----|-----|-----|-----
:-----|-----|-----|-----
    
```

Fig.2. Result of Evaluating annotation type “segmentation (segm)”

Fig.3. Result displaying of Inference Test.

Fig.4. Result displaying Image with damage

Fig.5. Result displaying Image with Scratches.

Achieving high accuracy in damage assessment, the integration of Mask R-CNN within the Detectron2 framework has demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in identifying and detailing automotive damage. This technique is quite good at identifying and classifying different kinds of damage, like scratches and serious impairments. Our analyses validate the model's ability to accurately identify and categorize damage, improving the efficiency of manual inspections and the handling of insurance and vehicle claims. With the use of sophisticated machine learning algorithms and a large dataset, this method increases the accuracy and operational effectiveness of automated automotive damage evaluations.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

The project's implementation phase focused on using the Mask R-CNN model to detect vehicle damage within the Detectron2 framework. The model was successfully trained to identify and distinguish between different kinds of car damage after being pretrained on a large dataset on Detectron2. The Gradio interface was created to make it simple for users to upload images, increasing the system's accessibility and usability.

The system uses the trained model to quickly and accurately detect damage and segment instances from uploaded photos. The technology analyzes these photos in real time, identifying the kind of damage, emphasizing any damage found, and instantly adding annotations to the pictures.

This configuration not only shows how sophisticated computer vision techniques may be used in real-world situations, but it also improves the effectiveness of procedures like processing insurance claims and estimating damage. The system is kept flexible and scalable by using an open-source framework such as Detectron2, making it appropriate for additional integration and development in a range of automotive applications.

Fig.6. Implementation of image with scratches

Fig.7. Implementation of image with damage

Achieving high accuracy in damage assessment, the integration of Mask R-CNN within the Detectron2 framework has demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in identifying and detailing automotive damage. This technique is quite good at identifying and classifying different kinds of damage, like scratches and serious impairments. Our analyses validate the model's ability to accurately identify and categorize damage, improving the efficiency of manual inspections and the handling of insurance and vehicle claims. With the use of sophisticated machine learning algorithms and a large dataset, this method increases the accuracy and operational effectiveness of automated automotive damage evaluations.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Car damage identification has advanced significantly with the use of advanced computer vision techniques such as Mask R-CNN, made possible by the Detectron2 framework. This development has profound consequences for the automotive sector. This technology makes it possible to analyze car damage quickly and accurately, improving vehicle safety, responding to collisions more quickly, and handling insurance claims more efficiently. Notably, it also contributes significantly to the efficiency and dependability of insurance procedures by precisely identifying discrepancies in damage reports, which helps to discover false claims. Additionally, it improves user experiences by giving vehicle owners the ability to evaluate damage and communicate easily with repair services via mobile applications. The advancements in

computer vision and open-source technologies are constantly changing and becoming more accessible. These developments hold the potential to improve safety, efficiency, and integrity in a variety of industries, hence having a substantial impact on consumer trust and operating standards.

VIII. References

- [1]. Kaiming He, Georgia Gkioxari, Piotr Dollar, Ross Girshick: Mask R-CNN, ICCV 2017.
- [2]. L. Plenka, COCO Car Damage Detection Dataset (2019).
- [3]. Facebook AI Research. "Detectron2", 2019
- [4] N. Dhieb, H. Ghazzai, H. Besbes, and Y. Massoud, "A Very Deep Transfer Learning Model for Vehicle Damage Detection and Localization," in Conf. Proc. IEEE, Dec. 2019.
- [5] K. Pasupa, P. Kittiworapanya, N. Hongngern, and K. Woraratpanya, "Evaluation of Deep Learning Algorithms for Semantic Segmentation of Car Parts, May 2021.
- [6] M. Y. J. A. Azmi, I. Ahmad, M. Z. Arefeen, D. Ahmed, and H. B. Mehare, "Vehicle Damaged Detection Using Deep Learning," IRJMETS, vol. 04, no. 09, Sep. 2022, Impact Factor- 6.752, [Online]. Available: www.irjmets.com.
- [7] D. Mallios, L. Xiaofei, N. McLaughlin, J. Martinez del Rincon, C. Galbraith, and R. Garland, "Vehicle Damage Severity Estimation for Insurance Operations Using In-The-Wild Mobile Images," IEEE Access, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3299223.